

PSYCHOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF WOMEN'S PROFESSIONAL SUCCESS

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Abstract: This article explains ideas about a woman's professional success in society and the tasks of combining family and professional roles to significantly increase a woman's need for self-awareness and material self-sufficiency in modern socio-economic conditions. It is explained that the types of professional areas of women depend on their success in life and the system of ideas about the social role of women in the modern world.

Keywords: Women, career path, life success, modern world, social role, career path, professional identity.

INTRODUCTION

Success is an event that, at first glance, has a clear meaning in life. But success is a multifaceted concept and is expressed in different ways in people's minds. The importance of ideas about success lies in the fact that they act as a mechanism for assessing the success of setting life goals and implementing life strategies. In addition, an attitude of success, a feeling of satisfaction from achieving a set goal, gaining prestige and status directly affects a person's psychological state, promotes professional self-awareness and is an incentive for personal improvement[1].

Often the concept of "success" is associated with career growth and self-awareness in the professional field. This is due to the fact that success is often viewed as an event that receives social and public evaluation. However, success is seen not only in the mirror of public opinion or in the recognition or non-

recognition of others. Self-assessment of success, mediated by a value system, life orientations, career prospects, etc., is important for personal development[5].

Currently, gender stereotypes prevail in society, according to which solving everyday problems is traditionally the prerogative of women, and professional issues are traditionally the prerogative of men. Based on this, professional activities and careers are largely the prerogative of men. However, in modern socio-economic conditions, women's need for self-realization and material self-sufficiency has increased significantly, so they have to combine family and professional roles. At the same time, a career in a woman's life becomes especially important[4].

In addition, in the public consciousness there are common ideas about which professions are "male" and which are "female", that is, gender roles and the "natural" division of labor by gender. In addition, the name of the profession often reflects its gender.

1. The uniqueness of ideas about "success" and "successful woman" is determined by the traditional or non-traditional nature of the professional role performed by women, as well as the characteristics of their attributional processes.

2. The types of women's career paths depend on their success in life and the system of ideas about the social role of women in the modern world.

3. Women in traditional and nontraditional professional roles differ in their different life goals and strategies for achieving them[3].

The theoretical and methodological foundations of our research were: the French school of studying social images (S. Moscovici, D. Jodlet), the theory of cognitive correspondence (F. Heider, T. Newcombe, L. Festinger), and the theory of attributes. (L. Ross, E. Jones, K. Davis, H. Kelly, D. Boehm, B. Weiner), general psychological theory of activity (A. N. Leontiev, S. L. Rubinstein), concept of social cognition (G. M Andreeva), the concept of human life or (K.A.

Abulkhanova-Slavskaya, S.L. Rubinstein), dispositional theories of personality (G. Allport, G. Eysenck, R. Kettel, V.A. Yadov), gender concepts (S. Bem), theories of career growth (E. Shane, D. Hall), role theories (V.I. Shuvanov, G. Mintzberg).

The uniqueness of ideas about the “successful woman” and the “success” of women in traditional and non-traditional professional roles is reflected in:

- women with traditional professional roles have adverbial ideas, according to which success is determined by an assessment of the social environment;
- Internal External;
- global identity; b) attribution error:
- underestimation of “unequal opportunities for role behavior”;
- “error of fictitious correlations”;
- self-serving biases.

3. A high level of similarity in the system of ideas about a “successful woman” was discovered between men and women performing non-traditional professional roles, which is expressed in the statement that a woman’s success is ensured by a set of specific personal qualities. . adjectives (type of “personal” ideas).

4. The leading professional areas of women performing traditional and non-traditional professional roles are determined:

- career paths “autonomy” and “lifestyle integration” are the main career development strategies for women in non-traditional professional roles;
- Career paths of “service” and “sustainability” are the main career strategies for women in traditional professional positions[2].

5. The main life goals and strategies for their implementation are analyzed:

- high level of reflexes in planning life goals; the presence of internal strategies for their implementation, based on the use of specific psychological qualities of women with non-traditional professional roles;

- low level of awareness and planning of their life goals, as well as the use of external strategies for their implementation, based on the involvement of external factors (support from the immediate environment, luck, a successful combination of situations, etc.), which are typical for women to have traditional professional roles.

- the presence of personal ideas, expressed in the need to possess certain psychological qualities that ensure success for women in non-traditional professional roles;

- the predominance of gender stereotypes that women performing traditional professional roles have limited opportunities for professional self-realization and a lack of psychological qualities necessary for successful career growth.

2. The uniqueness of the system of social ideas about success is determined by: a) stylistic features of the respondents' attribution processes:

The success of modern women lies in concretizing the ideas about traditional or non-traditional professional roles that they play. The conducted research allows us to identify the possibility of using the theory of social representation and the theory of cognitive correspondence as a general research approach on the basis of which one can assess the nature of a person's construction of his professional path. The effectiveness of using the basic rules of the concept of social ideas to divide various professions into "traditionally female" and "traditionally male" is shown. The theoretical data of the work are recommended for use in lecture courses and seminars on social psychology, personality psychology, gender psychology, and occupational psychology.

- when developing and implementing educational programs and trainings for personal and professional growth, it is advisable to use the identified systems of women's ideas about success in life and areas of career growth; in consulting work on creating personal strategies for career growth in traditionally male professions[2].

For women with a traditional professional role, the most important goals in life are: “achieving material wealth,” “children’s well-being and stability in the family.” 20 percent of women strive to achieve a high level of professionalism; for 16 percent, “their own health” is an important value. Half (50%) of women in non-traditional professional roles cite “children's well-being” and “family stability” as their top goals. We believe that the feeling of guilt associated with the lack of time spent with family leads to the fact that family, and especially children, become one of the most important values for women in this group in life.

Women have reached a certain level of self-awareness in the professional sphere, and therefore want to “stabilize” and improve the sphere of family relationships so that their lives are more harmonious. At the same time, success and career do not lose their importance (25% of women in this group want to continue moving up the career ladder). However, it was found that 14% of women in non-traditional professional roles reported a complete lack of purpose in life, that is, a loss of a certain meaning in life.

In modern psychology, an increasing number of researchers are turning to the analysis of the phenomenon of success. This is due to a number of reasons. First, social success, cultivated by the media, becomes almost a social norm. A person is largely assessed in terms of his social prestige. A person who has not achieved social recognition is often perceived as a loser, as a person who does not deserve due attention. Secondly, in modern Russian society there is a significant transformation of ideas about success, which in turn determine the path of personal, professional and generally social development of each individual. The nature of ideas about success is influenced by a variety of factors, including the specifics of the professional activity that a person performs. In turn, during the process of feminization of society, women are increasingly “penetrating” into traditionally male spheres of activity. An increasing number of women are

striving to prove themselves not only as “homemakers,” but as qualified professionals focused on career advancement. “Traditionality” or “unconventionality” of professional roles performed by women influences the specifics of ideas about success, which, in turn, act as a mechanism for setting life goals and assessing the success of implementing one’s life strategy.

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